

TWO NUMERICAL METHODS FOR THE RLW EQUATION

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, the numerical solutions of the regularized long wave (RLW) equation are obtained by using the extended cubic B-spline collocation method for space discretization and the Crank-Nicolson and Simpson's methods having different accuracy orders for time discretization. The accuracy of the methods is presented by computing the maximum error norm and conservation laws of the RLW equation. The robustness of the suggested methods is shown by a classical test problem.

Keywords: Collocation method; Crank-Nicolson method; Simpson's method; extended cubic B-spline function; regularized long wave equation.

AMS Subject Classification: 65M70; 65D07; 74J35.

1. INTRODUCTION

The frequently occurred nonlinear phenomena in the mathematical models of some nonlinear evolution equations are the propagation of the solitary waves in nonlinear dispersive media. This dispersive waves can be described using the following RLW equation with the positive parameters ε and μ :

$$u_t + u_x + \varepsilon uu_x - \mu u_{xxt} = 0. \quad (1.1)$$

The solutions of the RLW equation have been studied for many years by researchers and mostly the Galerkin [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] and collocation [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12] finite element methods based on various B-spline functions have been used in recent years. Also in this study, the collocation method based on extended cubic B-spline functions with similar properties to cubic B-spline functions, which are a well-known type of B-spline functions, have been used for obtaining the numerical solution of Eq.(1.1). Although the using of the extended B-spline functions are not as famous as the B-spline functions in the literature, they have been used in numerical solutions of different equations before. Hamid et al. have been used the extended cubic B-spline interpolation method for solving the second order linear two-point boundary value problems [13, 14]. A class of singular boundary value problems is solved by Goh [15] et al. using extended cubic uniform B-spline approximations. A numerical solution of the modified regularized long wave equation is obtained by the collocation method based on an extended cubic B-spline function [16]. The collocation method based on the extended B-spline functions is described for the numerical solutions of the advection-diffusion equation [17]. The Fisher's equation is solved numerically using extended B-spline collocation method [18]. A collocation method based on extended cubic B-spline functions is presented by Sharifi and Rashidinia for solving the telegraph equation [19]. In 2016, Heilat et al. proposed the extended cubic B-spline method for solving a linear system of second-order boundary value problems numerically [20]. To obtain the numerical solution of the time fractional advection-diffusion equation, a finite difference scheme based on extended cubic B-splines is set up in the study [21]. The extended cubic B-spline approximation is applied the time fractional Fisher equation to solve numerically [22]. The numerical solution of the inverse second-order one-dimensional hyperbolic telegraph equation is solved by the collocation method based on extended cubic B-spline basis functions [23].

Our main aim in this paper is to see that when we apply the collocation method based on extended cubic B-spline functions for the numerical solution of the RLW equation, what is the effect of order of the time discretization method.

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The organization of paper is as follows. In section 2, the extended cubic B-spline collocation methods based on different time discretization schemes as second and fourth orders are described for the numerical solution of the RLW equation. In section 3, one test problem is considered to see the efficiency of the proposed methods. Lastly, the results obtained by the proposed methods for the numerical experiments are compared with each other and with other methods in the literature.

2. EXTENDED CUBIC B-SPLINE COLLOCATION METHODS

Let us take a uniform mesh with the knots $x_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, N$ and equal space step h on $[c, d]$ and the following conditions of the Eq.(1.1):

$$\begin{aligned} u(c, t) &= \beta_1, \quad u(d, t) = \beta_2 \\ u_x(c, t) &= 0, \quad u_x(d, t) = 0, \quad t \in (0, T], \\ u(x, 0) &= g(x), \quad x \in [c, d]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

The exact solutions of the unknown functions at the grid points are described as follows

$$u(x_r, t_s) = u_r^s, \quad r = 0, 1, \dots, N; \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

where $x_r = c + rh$, $t_s = s\Delta t$ and the notation U_r^s is used to represent the numerical value of u_r^s . Rewriting the Eq. (1.1) as

$$v_t = (u - \mu u_{xx})_t = -(u_x + \varepsilon u u_x). \quad (2.2)$$

the time discretized form of the RLW equation can be obtained. Then using the following Crank-Nicolson and Simpson's methods in (2.2), respectively:

$$v^{s+1} = v^s + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \left((v_t)^{s+1} + (v_t)^s \right) + \mathcal{O}(\Delta t^3), \quad (2.3)$$

$$v^{s+1} = v^{s-1} + \frac{\Delta t}{3} \left((v_t)^{s+1} + 4(v_t)^s + (v_t)^{s-1} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\Delta t^5), \quad (2.4)$$

leads to

$$\begin{aligned} & u^{s+1} - \mu u_{xx}^{s+1} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} (u_x^{s+1} + \varepsilon u^{s+1} u_x^{s+1}) \\ = & u^s - \mu u_{xx}^s - \frac{\Delta t}{2} (u_x^s + \varepsilon u^s u_x^s), \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & u^{s+1} - \mu u_{xx}^{s+1} + \frac{\Delta t}{3} (u_x^{s+1} + \varepsilon u^{s+1} u_x^{s+1}) \\ = & -\frac{4\Delta t}{3} (u_x^s + \varepsilon u^s u_x^s) + u^{s-1} - \mu u_{xx}^{s-1} - \frac{\Delta t}{3} (u_x^{s-1} + \varepsilon u^{s-1} u_x^{s-1}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Thus, we have two different time discretization with the Crank-Nicolson method which is of order 2 and Simpson's method which is of order 4. To generalize these methods, the following formulation can be taken

$$v^{s+1} = \theta_1 v^s + \theta_2 v^{s-1} + \theta_3 (v_t)^{s+1} + \theta_4 (v_t)^s + \theta_5 (v_t)^{s-1} \quad (2.7)$$

and with using above equation in (2.2) the general form of the RLW equation with the time discretization methods can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} & u^{s+1} - \mu u_{xx}^{s+1} + \theta_3 (u_x^{s+1} + \varepsilon u^{s+1} u_x^{s+1}) \\ = & \theta_1 (u^s - \mu u_{xx}^s) - \theta_4 (u_x^s + \varepsilon u^s u_x^s) + \theta_2 (u^{s-1} - \mu u_{xx}^{s-1}) \\ & - \theta_5 (u_x^{s-1} + \varepsilon u^{s-1} u_x^{s-1}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

where if the parameters are chosen as $\theta_1 = 1, \theta_2 = 0, \theta_3 = \theta_4 = \Delta t/2, \theta_5 = 0$, the time discretization method is named as Crank-Nicolson method [24] (M1) and if they are chosen as $\theta_1 = 0, \theta_2 = 1, \theta_3 = \Delta t/3, \theta_4 = 4\Delta t/3, \theta_5 = \Delta t/3$, this one is named as Simpson's method (M2).

TABLE 1. Extended cubic B-spline values at the knot points.

x	x_{r-2}	x_{r-1}	x_r	x_{r+1}	x_{r+2}
$Q_r(x)$	0	$\frac{4-\lambda}{24}$	$\frac{8+\lambda}{12}$	$\frac{4-\lambda}{24}$	0
$Q'_r(x)$	0	$\frac{1}{2h}$	0	$-\frac{1}{2h}$	0
$Q''_r(x)$	0	$\frac{2+\lambda}{2h^2}$	$-\frac{2+\lambda}{h^2}$	$\frac{2+\lambda}{2h^2}$	0

The extended cubic B-spline $Q_r(x)$, which is produced in 2003 by Han and Liu [25], is defined as

$$Q_r(x) = \frac{1}{24h^2} \begin{cases} 4h(1-\lambda)(x-x_{r-2})^3 + 3\lambda(x-x_{r-2})^4, & x \in [x_{r-2}, x_{r-1}]; \\ (4-\lambda)h^4 + 12h^3(x-x_{r-1}) + 6h^2(2+\lambda)(x-x_{r-1})^2 \\ -12h(x-x_{r-1})^3 - 3\lambda(x-x_{r-1})^4, & x \in [x_{r-1}, x_r]; \\ (4-\lambda)h^4 + 12h^3(x_{r+1}-x) + 6h^2(2+\lambda)(x_{r+1}-x)^2 \\ -12h(x_{r+1}-x)^3 - 3\lambda(x_{r+1}-x)^4, & x \in [x_r, x_{r+1}]; \\ 4h(1-\lambda)(x_{r+2}-x)^3 + 3\lambda(x_{r+2}-x)^4, & x \in [x_{r+1}, x_{r+2}]; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

The values of $Q_r(x)$, $Q'_r(x)$ and $Q''_r(x)$ at the knots can be seen in Table 1.

To set up the space discretization of the Eq. (2.8), let we take the approximate solution U in terms for the extended cubic B-splines as

$$U(x, t) = \sum_{r=-1}^{N+1} Q_r(x) \delta_r(t) \quad (2.10)$$

where δ_i are time dependent unknowns which will be calculated. So, the approximate solution and their derivatives at the knots can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} U_r &= U(x_r, t) = \frac{4-\lambda}{24}\delta_{r-1} + \frac{8+\lambda}{12}\delta_r + \frac{4-\lambda}{24}\delta_{r+1}, \\ U'_r &= U'(x_r, t) = -\frac{1}{2h}\delta_{r-1} + \frac{1}{2h}\delta_{r+1}, \\ U''_r &= U''(x_r, t) = \frac{2+\lambda}{2h^2}\delta_{r-1} - \frac{2+\lambda}{h^2}\delta_r + \frac{2+\lambda}{2h^2}\delta_{r+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

Using (2.11) in (2.8), a fully-discretized form of the (1.1) is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} &\alpha_1 - \mu\gamma_1 - \theta_3\beta(1 + \varepsilon\eta^{s+1})\delta_{r-1}^{s+1} + (\alpha_2 + \mu\gamma_2)\delta_r^{s+1} \\ &+ (\alpha_1 - \mu\gamma_1 + \theta_3\beta(1 + \varepsilon\eta^{s+1}))\delta_{r+1}^{s+1} \\ = &(\theta_1(\alpha_1 - \mu\gamma_1) + \theta_4\beta(1 + \varepsilon\eta^s))\delta_{r-1}^s \\ &+ (\theta_1(\alpha_2 + \mu\gamma_2))\delta_r^s + (\theta_1(\alpha_1 - \mu\gamma_1) - \theta_4\beta(1 + \varepsilon\eta^s))\delta_{r+1}^s \\ &+ (\theta_2(\alpha_1 - \mu\gamma_1) + \theta_5\beta(1 + \varepsilon\eta^{s-1}))\delta_{r-1}^{s-1} \\ &+ (\theta_2(\alpha_2 + \mu\gamma_2))\delta_r^{s-1} + (\theta_2(\alpha_1 - \mu\gamma_1) - \theta_5\beta(1 + \varepsilon\eta^{s-1}))\delta_{r+1}^{s-1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

where $\alpha_1 = \frac{4-\lambda}{24}$, $\alpha_2 = \frac{8+\lambda}{12}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{2h}$, $\gamma_1 = \frac{2+\lambda}{2h^2}$, $\gamma_2 = \frac{2+\lambda}{h^2}$, $\eta^j = \alpha_1\delta_{r-1}^j + \alpha_2\delta_r^j + \alpha_1\delta_{r+1}^j$, $j = s-1, s, s+1$. Thus, we have a system of $N+1$ equation and $N+3$ unknowns. The boundary conditions $u(c, t) = \beta_1$, $u(d, t) = \beta_2$ are help us to eliminate the parameters δ_{-1} and δ_{N+1} so that we have a solvable $(N+1) \times (N+1)$ matrix system. The obtained matrix system is easily solved with Matlab packet program. To start the iteration of system, δ^0 have been determined by using the both of the conditions in Eq.(2.1), so then we can obtaine iteratively the δ^s at time $t^s = s\Delta t$. Since the system (2.12) is an implicit system due to the term δ , we have used an inner iteration.

3. TEST PROBLEMS

We have dealt with a test problem to demonstrate the given algorithm. The conservation laws satisfied by the RLW equation:

$$I_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u dx, I_2 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (u^2 + \mu(u_x)^2) dx, I_3 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (u^3 + 3u^2) dx, \quad (3.1)$$

are calculated by use of the trapezoidal rule in numerical experiments. The order of convergence of the methods are determined by the following formula:

$$\text{order} = \frac{\log \frac{(L_\infty)_{\Delta t_r}}{(L_\infty)_{\Delta t_{r+1}}}}{\log \frac{\Delta t_r}{\Delta t_{r+1}}}. \quad (3.2)$$

The accuracy of the method is calculated by the error norm:

$$L_\infty = \max_r |u_r - U_r| \quad (3.3)$$

and the determination of λ in the extended cubic B-spline is made by experimentally.

3.1. Motion of single solitary wave. The exact solution of RLW equation is

$$u(x, t) = 3\gamma \text{sech}^2(k[x - \tilde{x}_0 - vt]), \quad (3.4)$$

where $k = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon\gamma}{\mu(1+\varepsilon\gamma)}}$. The initial condition is worked out by taking $t = 0$ in Eq.(3.4). We have used the values of the boundary conditions as zero. The values of the parameters are chosen as $\gamma = 0.1$, $x_0 = 0$, $\varepsilon = 1$ and $\mu = 1$. The motion of the obtained single solitary wave with these parameters have been come about the interval $-60 \leq x \leq 90$ in time period $0 \leq t \leq 20$. The space and time steps are taken as $h = \Delta t = 0.1$ in numerical calculations.

In this test problem, the $\lambda = -0.0002669$ is determined by scanning the interval $[-1, 0]$ with the increment 0.0001 first, then according to the results scanning the interval $[-0.0003, -0.0002]$ with the increment 0.0000001. The solution profiles are depicted in Fig. 1 at selected times for M2. In this figure, it can be said that the peak of the solitary wave remained almost the same throughout the study period.

FIGURE 1. Solitary wave solutions.

The distribution of absolute errors for both proposed methods at $t = 20$ with $h = \Delta t = 0.1$ is figured in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2. Absolute error with $h = \Delta t = 0.1$ for the proposed methods.

The absolute error norms, the rate of convergence and the values of the conservation invariants I_1, I_2, I_3 of the proposed methods are listed in Table 2. To make a comparison with some early studies, the maximum errors with the conservation invariants are presented in Table 3. From these tables, it can be seen that M2 is one of the most accurate methods. The values of the conservation invariants I_1, I_2, I_3 at different times remain fairly the same when compared with the analytical invariants.

TABLE 2. Errors and invariants for amplitude $3\gamma = 0.3$ at time $t = 20$ with $-60 \leq x \leq 90$.

M1					
$h = \Delta t$	L_∞	order	I_1	I_2	I_3
2	2.8611×10^{-2}	1.68	3.9799509	0.8114492	2.5808278
1	8.9181×10^{-3}	1.90	3.9799497	0.8105560	2.5791898
0.5	2.3953×10^{-3}	2.00	3.9799497	0.8104692	2.5790207
0.2	3.8424×10^{-4}	2.11	3.9799497	0.8104627	2.5790078
0.1	8.9302×10^{-5}		3.9799497	0.8104625	2.5790075
M2					
$h = \Delta t$	L_∞	order	I_1	I_2	I_3
2	3.1096×10^{-3}	1.59	3.9799498	0.8102922	2.5784840
1	1.0325×10^{-3}	1.93	3.9799497	0.8104533	2.5789780
0.5	2.7185×10^{-4}	2.20	3.9799497	0.8104620	2.5790057
0.2	3.6210×10^{-5}	3.19	3.9799497	0.8104625	2.5790074
0.1	4.1704×10^{-6}		3.9799497	0.8104625	2.5790074
Exact			3.9799497	0.8104625	2.5790074

TABLE 3. Solitary wave amplitude=0.3 at $t = 20$ with $h = 0.125, \Delta t = 0.1$.

Method	$L_\infty \times 10^5$	I_1	I_2	I_3
M1($-60 \leq x \leq 90$)	9.57759	3.9799497	0.8104625	2.5790075
M2($-60 \leq x \leq 90$)	0.82616	3.9799497	0.8104625	2.5790074
M1($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	9.57759	3.9798839	0.8104625	2.5790075
M2($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	1.26845	3.9798839	0.8104625	2.5790074
[1]QBGM1($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	7.3	3.97988	0.81046	2.57900
[1]QBGM2($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	12.8	3.97988	0.81046	2.57900
[2]($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	7.344	3.9798879	0.8104622	2.5790063
[26]($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	25.398	3.97989	0.80925	2.57501
[26]($-80 \leq x \leq 120, h = 0.2$)	14.240	3.97829	0.80983	2.57692
[27]($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	8.6	3.97988	0.810465	2.57901
[28]($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	19.8	3.98206	0.811164	2.58133
[29]($-40 \leq x \leq 60$)	11.5	3.97988	0.8046	2.57900
CN1[30]($-80 \leq x \leq 100$)	8.78896	3.9799498	0.8104273	2.5790075
CN2[30]($-80 \leq x \leq 100$)	8.79019	3.9799498	0.8104273	2.5790075
AM1[30]($-80 \leq x \leq 100$)	0.20615	3.9799498	0.8104625	2.5790074
AM2[30]($-80 \leq x \leq 100$)	0.21010	3.9799498	0.8104298	2.5790159
Exact		3.9799497	0.8104625	2.5790074

4. CONCLUSION

The collocation method based on extended cubic B-spline as weight and trial functions for space discretization of the RLW equation is used. Two methods having different accuracy orders for time discretization have been proposed to get the numerical solution to the RLW equation. By examining a well known test problem which is the investigation of the motion of the single solitary wave is shown that the proposed methods are performed well. By comparing both of the proposed methods with previous studies, it is seen that the M2 gives accurate and reliable results to get the numerical solution of the RLW equation.

Acknowledgement. This work is presented at International Conference on Mathematical Advances and Applications (ICOMAA2018) in İstanbul, Türkiye on 11-13 May 2018.

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